

Navadhanya pinda sweda in clinical astrology

Supriya Mishra *, Ashvini kumar M and Lohith BA

Department of panchakarma, SDMCAH, HASSAN, Karnataka, India. 573201.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 26(01), 504-507

Publication history: Received on 24 February 2025; revised on 01 April 2025; accepted on 04 April 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.26.1.1051>

Abstract

Navadhanya Pinda Sweda, which falls under the category of *Swedana* (sudation therapy), is believed to balance the *doshas*, improve circulation, alleviate pain, and promote detoxification. Clinical astrology, an integrative approach that combines astrological insights with medical practice, has gained attention for its ability to assess and influence health conditions based on planetary positions and their effects on the individual's constitution. This paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the synergistic effects of *Navadhanya Pinda Sweda* and clinical astrology, offering insights into their potential for managing chronic pain, inflammation, Degenerative diseases and musculoskeletal disorders, while promoting overall health and vitality.

Keywords: *Navadhanya pinda sweda*; *Swedana*; Clinical astrology; Degenerative diseases

1. Introduction

In Ayurveda following causes of disease has described¹

- Mithya ahara vihara janya
- Asatmya indriyarth samyog
- Prajnaaparadh janya
- Kalaj
- Karmaj

Karmaj vyadhi are those in which we can see the *hetu* are very less but the impact of disease is more eg. Degenerative diseases. This type of *vyadhi* needs special attention for *Daivavyapashraya chikitsa*. Planetary movements definitely effect the human psycho-physiological aspects who is but a tiny part of this same universe composed of same elements (*panchamahabhoot*) e.g. high and low tides due to gravitational force of moon could have some effects on human system that are filled with water 90%. even bones contain 65% water or we can see episodes of epilepsy follows lunar calendar². *Navagrahas* or Nine planets have great importance in human lives and astrology, responsible for all good and bad times , one faces in life. Diseases are also believed to exist due to malefic planets in strong positions of person's *kundali*. In *Ashtang ayurved* , acharyas has given the equal importance of graha chikitsa. Ayurveda uses herbal remedies to treat diseases.As such they are also effective for planetary imbalances responsible for diseases.That's why an ayurvedic physicians should apply graha chikitsa / Clinical Astrlogy in every aspects of treatment to get better results. The planets and stars in astronomy also represent the qualities of the Doshas.

* Corresponding author: Supriya Mishra

Table 1 Relation to *Navgrahas* with *dosha*³

Vata	Saturn- Moon- Rahu
Pitta	Sun- Mars- Ketu
Kapha	Jupiter- Venus
Samavastha or vishamavastha	Mercury

Table 2 Relation to *Navgrahas* in many context such as grains , body parts ,gemstones etc.^{4,5}

Planets	Grains	Body Parts	Gems	Herbs	Dosha
Sun	Wheat	Bones	Ruby	<i>Bilwamool</i>	<i>Pitta Kapha</i> <i>Kapha-vata Jala</i> <i>Vata</i>
Moon	Rice	Muscles and blood	Pearl	<i>Khirika</i>	<i>Vata-kapha</i>
Mars	Red lentil	Marrow and profuse bleeding disorder	Coral	<i>Anantmool</i>	<i>Rakta - Pitta</i>
Mercury	Green gram	Skin diseases	Emerald	<i>Brindhawarakamool</i>	<i>Tridosha</i>
Jupiter	Split gram lentil(Chana dal)	Fat metabolism	Yellow Sapphire	<i>Brahmajatimool</i>	<i>Kapha</i>
Venus	Soya gram	Fertility	Diamond	<i>Rambasakmool</i>	<i>Kapha -Vata</i>
Saturn	Black sesame	Ligaments & Muscles	Blue Sapphire	<i>Swetberelamool</i>	<i>Vata</i>
Rahu	Black gram	Muscular system	Zircon	<i>Shwetchandanmool</i>	<i>Vata</i>
Ketu	Horse gram	Bleeding disorder	Cat's eye	<i>Aswagandha</i>	<i>Pitta</i>

In Ayurveda, planets are believed to influence health by affecting *Panchamahabhootas* and *doshas*. For example, the Sun, linked to Pitta, causes heat-related diseases, while the Moon, associated with *Vata* and *Kapha*, is tied to cold-related ailments. The planets also impact the natural world, influencing the growth and medicinal properties of plants. Classical texts like the *Charaka Samhita* recommend specific times for administering treatments based on planetary alignments. This study aims to explore the relationship between planets and plants, understanding how the celestial bodies affect both health and nature. There is a belief that worshipping these planets can ward off misfortune from past karmas. Moving to the physical health benefits of *Navadhanya*, the nine grains used in practice (offered to the nine planets) have varied health benefits and can be used to bring balance to *Doshas*.

2. Materials and Methods

- Navdhanya each 50 gm
- Balamoola 250 gm
- Water - 4 lt
- Cow milk- 1lt
- Kora cloth (45cm X 45cm) - 4 pieces
- Threads(75cm) - 4
- Vessels - 3
- Oil for talam - 10ml
- Rasnadi churna - 5gm
- Suitable oil for abhyanga - 100ml
- Therapist - 2/4

2.1. Preparation Method

- **Balamoola kwatha preparation** - 250gm *kwatha choorna* +4 lt of water boil and reduce to 1 litre *Navadhanya* cooking- first make coarse powder, soak overnight or 5hrs in Q.S.water then boil or cooked with 0.5ltr of milk and 0.5ltr of *balamoola kwath*,cooked *dhanya* divided into 4 equal parts and put into 4 pieces of kora cloth make pottali and put pottali in the mixture of *balamoola* and *ksheer kwath* .
- **Poorvakarma ,pradhana &pashchat karma**- same as *shashtilkashali pinda sweda*⁶
- **Indications & Contraindications** - same as *shashtilkashali pinda sweda*

3. Result and Discussion

In astrology, donation and bathing of these nine grains according to the planets is suggested to get relief from diseases⁷. In Ayurveda many properties described about these nine grains which is helpful to treat various disease.

Table 3 Navdhanya & their properties⁸

Grains	Properties
Wheat	<i>Sandhankrit ,Vatahara,brimhan,vrishya ,snigdha ,sthairyakara</i>
Rice	<i>Tridoshashamak,sthairyakrit,snigdha,brimhan,balyakrit shukral</i>
Red lentil	<i>Pittashleshmaghna,laghu,sheeta,madhur, Supeshu alepaneshu cha</i>
Green gram	<i>Shkeshmapittaghna,netrya,sheeta,ruksha ,supyottamah</i>
Split gram (chana)	<i>Balyakrit, Pittakaphaghna</i>
Soya gram	<i>Kaphapittaghan,balya,sheet,brimhan</i>
Black Sesame	<i>Vatashamak,balya,twachya,stanya,vranehitah</i>
Black Gram	<i>Param vrishya,Vatashamak,punsatva,balya</i>
Horse gram	<i>Kapha vatashamak ,sweda sangrahaak, medojwarhar,krimihar</i>

Navdhanya Pinda Sweda is effective in treating a variety of diseases, particularly those that involve tissue depletion or weakness, as it focuses on *Brimhana* (nourishment) to counter tissue loss. The treatment's emphasis on *Ushna* (hot) and *Snigdha* (unctuous) qualities ensures deeper penetration into the tissues, stimulating circulation and nourishing the tissues from within. Unlike cold therapies, which tend to act on the surface, the *Ushnata*(heat) and *Snigdhatata*(unctuousness) in *Navdhanya Pinda Sweda* reach deeper layers, enhancing the therapeutic effect. Furthermore, *Rasayana* (rejuvenative) therapy is most beneficial when used after improving tissue conductivity. This is because cells initially resist nutrient absorption due to poor conductivity, but once it is improved through the heating and nourishing actions of the therapy, the cells become more receptive to the vital nutrients provided. As a result, the combined approach of *Ushna*, *Snigdha*, and *Rasayana* therapies optimizes tissue regeneration, balances the *doshas*, and promotes overall health, aiding in the effective treatment of conditions such as degenerative diseases, musculoskeletal disorders, and post-traumatic recovery. The therapy, therefore, not only helps in reversing tissue depletion but also in rejuvenating the body's natural resilience and vitality.

4. Conclusion

Thus, combining the power of Ayurveda with clinical astrology offers a profound and personalized treatment strategy that not only addresses the physical ailments but also aligns with the cosmic rhythms, promoting holistic healing. Further research in this area could help establish a deeper understanding of how planetary movements influence health and disease, enhancing the practice of Ayurveda and improving therapeutic outcomes for patients.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Govinda Raju U, Usha VNK. Daivavyapashray Chikitsa. 1st ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2017: 2-3.
- [2] Govinda Raju U, Usha VNK. Daivavyapashray Chikitsa. 1st ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 2017 : 194.
- [3] Kumari B, Singh S, Sinha UC. Correlation of Ayurveda and astrology on health. Ayushdhara. July-August 2022 July-August 2022; 9 : 86-89.
- [4] Dwivedi JN. Inter relationship of Ayurveda and Astrology. AYU. 2016 Sep 28; 34 :26-35.
- [5] Dwivedi JN. Inter relationship of Ayurveda and Astrology. AYU. 2016 Sep 28; 34 :26-35.
- [6] Verma J, Gopesh M, Gunjan G. Shashtika Shali Pinda Sweda (A Unique Bolus Massage): A Review Article. J AYUSH: Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Siddha Homeopathy. 2021;8(2):26-30.
- [7] Jha R. Manasagari, Janmpatraprabodh. Varanasi: Thakur Prasad and Sons; Year. p. 490-492
- [8] Thakral KK. Sushruta Samhita, Sutrasthana, Chapter 46. In: Thakral KK, editor. Sushruta Samhita. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 2023: 546-560.